

Drivers and barriers to social acceptance of carbon capture, utilisation and storage: A systematic literature review of survey-based studies

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ABSTRACT

Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) refers to a suite of technologies that can play an important role to decarbonise the energy and industry sectors. However, it is often argued that CCUS faces social acceptance issues. After more than 20 years of extensive research on this topic, this article provides a systematic literature review to assess the level of social acceptance of CCUS and analyse the role and importance of existing drivers and barriers for this acceptance. The results show that, overall, social acceptance of CCUS is neutral to slightly positive, being generally less preferred than other climate mitigation options. The most relevant drivers include perception of benefits (particularly effectiveness in climate change mitigation), knowledge of CCUS and trust on relevant stakeholders. In addition to proximity to a CCUS facility, the main barriers are related to perceived technological risks and leakage. The article identifies some knowledge gaps on the topic and proposes several avenues for further research. It also derives some policy implications from the research.

1. - Introduction

Given the negative consequences of climate change, greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) abatement has become an urgent need [1]. Several mitigation technologies and options exist and many of them are already commercially available. Those include renewable electricity technologies, energy conservation and efficiency, electrification and the use of green hydrogen in end-use sectors, amongst others [i.e., 2]. Nevertheless, some carbon emissions from fossil fuel use in a few hard-to-abate industrial processes may remain in 2050 [3,4]. Carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS) refer to a suite of technologies that can play an important and diverse role to decarbonise the energy and industry sectors [5].¹

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), among others, underline the critical role that CCUS plays to meet climate mitigation targets [1,6].² CCUS can achieve decarbonisation goals in hard-to-abate

industrial sectors (such as cement, petrochemical and steel industries) [1,7–10], as existing options are not considered to be sufficient to significantly reduce emissions in these sectors without the use of CCUS [1,10]. Several major CO₂ emitting countries envision the use of CCUS as a mitigation option, including the US [11,12], China [13–16], EU countries [17] and countries in South East Asia [18]. However, only 62 CCUS facilities currently operate worldwide [19]. This number has remained relatively stagnant over time, with only 1 to 3 projects added each year until 2023 and 2024, when 9 and 8 projects entered the operational phase, respectively [19]. These are low numbers compared to the deployment of other decarbonisation and climate mitigation technologies. They are also behind expectations [20], and below the modelled 1.5° pathway needs [1].³

This low deployment level is associated to certain difficulties, including technological and economic viability, but also to concerns about the operational safety and long-term integrity of CO₂ storage, transport risks, regulatory and institutional barriers, and limited public

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¹ In this review, we use carbon capture utilisation and storage (CCUS) as an umbrella term encompassing CO₂ capture, transport, storage, and utilisation technologies, unless stated otherwise. Many papers only refer to the stages of carbon capture and storage (CCS) and do not include utilisation. In others, the utilisation stage is explicitly included (CCUS). While transport is not explicitly considered in the CCS or CCUS acronyms, it is implicit in the storage and utilisation stages.

² [6] showed that a reduction of 36.9 gigatonnes (Gt) of CO₂ emissions was needed until 2050 to achieve the 1.5° pathway, of which 6% corresponded to CCS [6].

³ According to Ref. [19], the CCUS facilities in operation have a total annual capture capacity of almost 70 Mt CO₂.

acceptance [1,9,21]. Indeed, the latter has traditionally been regarded as one of the most important barriers for CCUS [1,6,9]. Hence, it is a main factor that needs to be accounted for when evaluating the potential future role of these technologies. This article addresses this issue. Its aim is to identify the level of social acceptance of CCUS and its drivers and barriers, using a systematic literature review of quantitative survey-based studies.

The focus of the review is on surveys to the general public, as we are interested in social acceptance by the general population and not by specific stakeholders or subgroups of the population, who may be more familiarised with CCUS or be biased towards certain aspects of it. Since CCUS is likely to play a role in CO₂ emission reductions, it is important to understand its degree of acceptance by the general population. Survey-based studies have the potential to provide a large amount of primary information on CCUS social acceptance and its drivers and barriers, which can be compared under a common methodological approach. Surveys are, indeed, the most common method used to analyse CCUS acceptance [22].

Some literature reviews of social acceptance of CCUS have already been published [9,22,23]. Based on 45 articles between 2002 and 2012, [24] identified the factors related to public acceptance in each article and included them in 12 categories.⁴ However, a ranking of the relevance of those factors was not provided. [9] reviewed 135 articles on the public perception of CCS. They found that effectiveness in climate change mitigation, the perception of benefits, information on CCS and trust were drivers to CCS acceptance, whereas NIMBY, perceived risks and mitigation deterrence were barriers [23]. [23] conducted a systematic meta-narrative review of 53 peer-reviewed publications on community acceptance of site-specific CCUS projects between 2009 and 2021. Their analysis identified nine dimensions that illustrated the underlying dynamics shaping the understanding of acceptance. More recently, [22] have carried out a systematic literature review to study public perceptions of CCUS globally, based on 88 peer-reviewed papers published between 2016 and 2024. The authors discuss positive, neutral and negative perceptions of CCUS and the factors influencing them. They find that positive perceptions are positively affected by knowledge and awareness of CCUS technologies and trust in government and developers, among others, whereas perception of CCUS is negatively affected by the high costs and risks of the technologies and lack of trust and knowledge.

Compared to those reviews, ours is different in several respects (see section 2 and Appendix 1 for details). We provide a quantitative and systematic analysis of the relevance of each factor at a high level of disaggregation, identifying its relevance, the net effect on CCUS acceptance (whether it is a driver or a barrier) and the level of evidence and agreement on this net effect. Therefore, it covers an important gap in the literature. In addition, it proposes a detailed future research agenda, based on the knowledge gaps found in the literature on CCUS acceptance research.

Our paper can be situated within the broader and more conceptual literature on the social acceptance of energy technologies (e.g., Refs. [26–29]).⁵ We consider all the relevant factors included in the reviewed literature, which has used different perspectives and followed different disciplinary traditions, including Economics, Sociology, Human Geography, Social Psychology and Cultural Theory, among others, in line with the integrated approach developed by [27]. The authors propose three general principles relating to social acceptance: 1) that the

⁴ These categories are based on the Technology Acceptance Framework (TAF) by Ref. [25] and include: experience, knowledge, trust, procedural fairness, distributive fairness, positive affect, negative affect, perceived costs, perceived risks, perceived benefits, outcome efficacy and problem perception.

⁵ Some papers on acceptance of energy technologies have previously been published in this journal, mostly on nuclear [30,31] or renewables [32,33], but not on CCUS.

components of individual acceptance include attitudinal elements, behavioural intentions and actual behaviours. 2) that there are three levels for the analysis of the social acceptance of a technology, i.e., the macro, meso and micro levels (e.g., countries, communities or individuals); 3) that social acceptance at these levels can refer to different “actors”, such as consumers, citizens (i.e., public), stakeholders or politicians. As proposed by Ref. [26], the three dimensions of acceptance analysis include community acceptance (the specific acceptance of siting decisions and energy projects by residents and local authorities), market acceptance (the process of market adoption of an innovation) and sociopolitical acceptance (acceptance of technologies and policies on the broadest level by the public, key stakeholders and policy makers). At this last level, research has tried to understand the levels of social acceptance (by the general public, policy makers, civil society organisations, experts or private organisations) at the country, state or regional level for a given energy technology [26,27].

The literature on the social acceptance of energy technologies has experienced several trends. According to Ref. [34], its geographical scope has shifted gradually from the focus in two countries (the US and the UK) towards the rest of the world, and social acceptance as a political issue has shifted to social acceptance as a psychological issue, and from the study of community acceptance of wind power to the combination of individual-level contextual and psychological determinants of perceptions and attitudes vis-à-vis large-scale electricity system technologies and/or projects, including CCUS [34]. Finally, research has been grouped more by technology and intellectual heritage than by the type of acceptance dimension [34].

Recent contributions have proposed future trajectories for social acceptance research in energy technologies, calling for an analysis of the dynamics in social acceptance [35] and the influence of different factors, time, power, and scale in shaping decision-making processes [29], asking for more sophisticated conceptual framing [27], for the inclusion of the role of power, dynamics between local and national actors and the role of emotions [29], for an analysis of the interrelation between the three dimensions of social acceptance [28,35] and for a greater focus on social acceptance as a political issue rather than as a psychological one [35]. At a methodological level, [29] calls for more experimental research in the area of dynamics of social acceptance, including choice experiments and extending the analysis beyond OECD countries, whereas [28] proposes the use of new data collection methods such as social media. This author also calls for understanding people's responses to (renewable) energy technologies as set against the background of “neoliberal capitalist societies” [28], analysing the dynamics of people's responses to renewable energy technologies over time, at local, national and global levels and investigating social conflict over renewable energy technologies not as a problem, but as participation.

This article takes up some of these propositions. It is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the methodology. The results are provided and discussed in Section 3. Section 4 discusses the policy implications of the research, whereas section 5 identifies the knowledge gaps in the literature and suggests several directions for future research. Section 6 closes with some conclusions and limitations of our research.

2. - Methodology

2.1. Aims and search strategy

This systematic review (SR) identifies survey-based articles on the social acceptance of CCUS by the general public in order to answer the following two questions:

- What has been the level of social acceptance for CCUS technologies in the scientific literature?
- Which are the most relevant drivers and barriers to the social acceptance of CCUS?

A comprehensive search strategy was defined based on keywords covering CCUS acceptance in a broad sense and, thus, geographical or temporal restrictions were not included. Then, the search strategy was operationalised with two complementary searches. Full details are provided in the following subsections.

2.2. Our approach compared to the existing reviews

Our review differs from previous CCUS acceptance reviews in several respects. Appendix 1 summarises these differences. We focus on specific factors and quantitatively identify whether they are drivers or barriers to CCUS acceptance, and their relevance, agreement and evidence on the net effect, following the method proposed in Refs. [36,37]. Thus, our article descends to the lowest possible level of such analysis (the specific factors). For the articles included in this research, we identify the specific drivers and barriers and their relevance and direction of effect. Each paper was read and the role of specific factors was coded manually. This allowed us to build a database with the factors in each article, from which we inferred conclusions about the relevance, net effect (direction) and level of agreement and evidence of each article. Previous reviews have not identified the exact relationship in the literature between a given factor and the acceptance of CCUS, i.e., those reviews have not identified the net effect of the different factors influencing CCUS acceptance in the reviewed papers. Their analysis of the factors has been carried out at a high level of aggregation. The closest to our paper in this sense is [22], which identifies some papers that include factors (which are broader than in our review) with a positive or a negative impact on acceptance, but this is done neither systematically nor quantitatively. They identify the number of times that an article includes one of 10 broad factors. In contrast, we believe that it is not sufficient just to state the number of times that a given factor has been used. First, such factor may have been included in the study, but may have been irrelevant, i.e. without an influence on acceptance (“relevance” dimension). In addition, a given factor may have opposing effects, being a driver of acceptance in some papers and a barrier in others (“direction” dimension). Furthermore, it is also important to know the number of papers which identify the factor as relevant (“evidence” dimension) and the extent to which there is agreement in the literature on the direction of the effect (“agreement” dimension).

2.3. The systematic literature review approach

A SR provides a meticulous summary of the available research in response to a research question, adopting a holistic view. Its aim is to identify, analyse and guide the interpretation of potentially large bodies of existing scientific evidence from multiple disciplines, with different methodologies, and different geographic and temporal contexts [38]. It deepens and synthesises the contents of the literature through a transparent and reproducible methodology [39].⁶ A traditional (narrative) review provides an unstructured exploratory evaluation of the literature in a particular area. It typically lacks transparency and replicability and is more subject to researcher bias compared to other methods, mainly regarding the inclusion and exclusion of research. These reviews may miss relevant research or place an excessive reliance on individual studies. In contrast, a SR adheres to a strict pre-established protocol, uses an explicit and replicable research design, ensures comprehensiveness in the literature search, and reduces bias in the selection of studies [41].

SRs are often used to inform further research and policy decisions on a topic that has been subject to previous heterogeneous research [42], as with the social acceptance of CCUS. SRs have increasingly been performed in the field of climate and energy studies, particularly for

low-carbon technologies such as renewables or energy efficiency [see, e.g., [38,43,44]]. However, with the exception of [22], they have not been used to analyse the social acceptance of CCUS so far.

2.4. Conceptual clarifications

Some terms and concepts used throughout this paper should be defined in a precise manner. The first one is “social acceptance”. As mentioned above, [26] distinguishes between three dimensions of acceptance: sociopolitical acceptance, community acceptance and market acceptance. On the other hand, acceptance and acceptability are often used interchangeably, but they are different concepts [45]. From a linguistic point of view, acceptance refers to the act of accepting, whereas acceptability is a property of the item to be accepted [46]. Whereas acceptability refers to the a priori perceived use and the complex processes underneath, acceptance refers to the actual use and outcome of such processes [47,48]. In this article, we use the term “acceptance” rather than “acceptability” for three reasons: 1) it is used in the aforementioned three-dimensional framework of [26]; 2) it refers to whether something is accepted or not, as opposed to mapping more complex, dynamic and hierarchical discussions of collective choice [49]; and 3) it is more consistent with the terminology used in public perception research on CCS [46], but also of energy technologies more broadly (e.g., [27,29]).

Some authors also distinguish between “perception” and “acceptance” [50,51]. For [50], the former refers to individual assessments of (dis)advantages and risks associated with a technology, its infrastructures, processes, products, and usage contexts, that influence and form acceptance. In contrast, “acceptance” would be a positive attitude or supporting behavior of the development, implementation or usage of technologies. Public perceptions and technology acceptance are closely intertwined, as the former significantly influences the latter [51]. Many authors use both terms interchangeably [e.g., [52]]. We follow this approach in our paper, although we generally use the term “acceptance”.⁷

Our SR also includes CCUS studies focusing on social preferences and willingness-to-pay (WTP) metrics for assessing CCUS social acceptance, as well as drivers and barriers. Although social preferences (WTP-based) and social acceptance are not conceptually similar, the former can be considered as a specific manifestation of the latter that include detailed and interchangeable aspects related to the implementation of the technology, independently of whether it is accepted or not. This interpretation seems to be in line with the more general literature on social acceptance, e.g. Ref. [34], which includes WTP/preference studies “as the most economics-oriented of the intellectual bases” of social acceptance [34, p.150] or [29], who argue that there should be “more experimental research in the area of dynamics of social acceptance, including choice experiments” [29, p.7]. WTP elicitation processes also involve cognitive trade-offs. This is in contrast to general attitude and perception questions, which largely involve affective responses. But these can be considered as complementary approaches when assessing social acceptance of CCUS, with WTP studies further contributing to economic insights and revealing the stability of public preferences when faced with specific cost constraints. WTP-based multi-attribute choice experiments also elicit preferences and trade-offs for specific characteristics and outcomes of CCUS projects or policies. Social preferences can also be assessed even if there is not acceptance at the individual level although, when combined in the same questionnaire, acceptance is usually assessed first and preferences later. WTP-based experiments normally include an opt-out (or status quo) alternative that would correspond to not accepting the technology or, at the very least, not accepting the possible CCUS implementation alternatives presented in

⁶ It is different from a narrative literature review, because it is “a self-contained research project in itself that explores a clearly specified question, usually derived from a policy or practice problem, using existing studies” [40].

⁷ It should be acknowledged that, although the paper uses the term “acceptance”, the empirical data largely reflect ex-ante acceptability.

these experiments. Therefore, an analysis of social preferences usually includes an implicit assessment of acceptance, while further providing more details about how the technology would be preferred to be implemented by the general public.

2.5. Study selection and data collection

To perform the SR, we adopted the best practice suggested by the literature (see, e.g. Refs. [41,43,53]), and followed 5 steps: 1) Definition of a search strategy for the SR, the aim of the SR and inclusion and exclusion criteria; 2) searches in the Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus databases (initial selection),⁸ plus manual searches in existing specialised journals and snowballing of references; 3) screening, i.e. application of the exclusion/inclusion criteria to the title and abstract (final selection); 4) content analysis (coding) and; 5) analysis and synthesis of the collected evidence. Fig. 1 provides an overview of this process.

Specifically, the search was carried out in the WoS and Scopus databases in July 2025. The search terms were applied to title, abstract and keywords, and the search was operationalised through the following query:

Topic (abstract, title, keywords) = (CCS OR CCU OR CCUS) AND
(social AND (*accept* OR *reject*))

Then, the following filters were applied. For “types”, all papers, review papers and conference papers were selected, in line with the aforementioned recommendations for SRs in energy research. For “categories”, all energy, economic, business, psychological and sociological categories were chosen. The language filter was English. We defined several inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 1).⁹

As our research focused on acceptance by the general public, studies specifically referring to policy makers, industry experts or other stakeholders were excluded. The data collection method was restricted to surveys as a means to obtain primary data. Regarding data treatment, only articles which reported at least basic descriptive statistical data of quantitative results were included. The results from WoS and Scopus were manually merged and duplicates were eliminated. Using the findings from the databases, complementary searches were carried out, following standard SR procedures [41]. These included a journal-by-journal analysis of key climate and energy journals and snowballing¹⁰.

This procedure led to the final sample, i.e. the identification and selection of 259 potentially relevant papers in the WoS database and 221 papers in the Scopus database. After applying the above-mentioned filters, 252 and 209 publications remained, respectively. 105 papers were duplicates in both databases and were removed, resulting in 356 unique contributions. These were screened and the exclusion and inclusion criteria were applied. 63 articles were identified to be within the scope of our review (see Appendix 2). The manual searches and snowballing led to 21 additional publications. Therefore, the final set of relevant papers for our SR was 84 publications. Fig. 1 provides an overview of this process.

2.6. Analysing and synthesising the collected evidence

The reviewed articles cover a wide range of factors (drivers and barriers) potentially influencing the acceptance of CCUS technologies. The identified factors were summarised, systematised and analysed,

⁸ WOS and Scopus are considered the two major scientific literature databases [54].

⁹ Appendix 2 provides information on the different reasons for excluding articles from this SR.

¹⁰ These journals were: International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, Climate Policy, Risk Analysis, Energy Research & Social Science, Energy Policy, Energy Economics and Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews.

following a procedure developed by the authors. First, all factors were grouped according to 11 overarching categories of drivers and barriers to CCUS acceptance identified in the literature: 1) sociodemographics; 2) proximity, place of residence and local acceptance; 3) benefit and risk perception; 4) political ideology, worldviews, climate change awareness, environmental awareness; 5) knowledge of CCUS; 6) contribution to climate change mitigation; 7) technoeconomic features; 8) environmental and security of supply benefits; 9) trust; 10) information provision; 11) economic impacts. Table 2 lists the different factors classified by category and briefly describes them.

Second, each factor was categorised according to the proposed classification framework, based on four evaluation criteria (“relevance”, “direction”, “evidence” and “agreement”). Each individual factor was quantified in each evaluation criterion on a 5-point Likert scale (from “very low” to “very high”), based on the analysed papers (the outcome of this SR). The idea was not only to identify if a given factor was considered as a driver or a barrier in the literature because, e.g. there were more articles in which the factor was a driver than a barrier (direction), but also to assess whether there was sufficient evidence to state so and the level of agreement on such direction, i.e. if many more articles identified it as a driver than as a barrier (high agreement) or the difference was very small (low agreement). The respective thresholds for each criterion are provided in Table 3. The numbers used for the thresholds could be considered subjective and arbitrary, but they are also relative to the outcome of the review. They are related to the number of papers included in this specific review, and not to any pre-established criterion in the literature. The thresholds can be regarded as intermediate values within a continuum defined by two extremes (“very low”/“very high”). Then, the intermediate levels are defined by splitting the range in five portions with the same size (Table 3).

Coding of the factors related to social acceptance was done manually by one of the researchers, and checked by the other two. We built three excel sheets, one in which the factor was not relevant in the sense of not being “statistically significant” (or the factor did not have a high importance if only descriptive statistics had been used), and two other sheets with the “drivers” and the “barriers” of social acceptance, depending on whether the reviewed article included it as a driver or as a barrier. For each article, we looked to the regression tables and included those factors which were not statistically significant into the “not relevant” sheet. When the factor was statistically significant, we looked at the sign of the respective coefficient and included it in either the “drivers” or “barrier” sheet. For each factor, we then counted the number of times in which it was not relevant and, if relevant, whether it was a driver or a barrier.

For a specific factor, “relevance” would be very high if a statistically significant relationship between that factor and CCUS acceptance could be identified (when inferential methods were used) or if the factor was explicitly considered as important (when a descriptive statistics approach was followed).¹¹ Based on all previous contributions in this SR that include that specific factor, a “relevance index” was built, taking into account the number of articles in which the factor appeared as relevant divided by the total number of articles in which the factor was included.¹² The factor was “very relevant” when the index was above 80%, meaning that this factor was either statistically significant or important (with descriptive statistics) in more than 80% of the papers which included the factor. It was “relevant” when it was between 60% and 80%, “medium” when such percentage was between 40% and 60%,

¹¹ In other words, relevance is understood in a broader meaning, i.e. it does not only refer to “statistical significance”. When descriptive statistics were used, a given factor was coded as “important” in a particular article if it was at the top of the list of either drivers or barriers in that article.

¹² Note that the “total number of articles” for the relevance criterion does not refer to the 84 articles in this review, but only to those articles that included the specific factor (which could then be either relevant or not relevant).

Fig. 1. PRISMA flow diagram. Source. Own elaboration.

Table 1
Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Category	Criteria
Type of interviewees	General public
Stages of CCUS Scope	Carbon capture, transportation, CO ₂ storage, and utilisation Geographic: Global Temporal: 2002-2025
General/local acceptance	Both general acceptance and local acceptance were addressed.
Data collection method	Quantitative data gathered in surveys to the general public.
Data treatment	The articles had to be explicit on their quantitative results and transparent on how these were obtained, i.e., through quantitative methods.

Note: The full list of exclusion criteria is provided in Appendix 2.

“low” when it was between 20% and 40%, and “very low” when it was lower than 20%.

For those articles for which the specific item was considered “relevant” in the aforementioned sense, we further identified whether it was positively or negatively related to CCUS acceptance (i.e., if it was either a driver or a barrier). Therefore, each item was considered a barrier or a

driver in the criterion “direction”, depending on the number of articles in which it appeared as a driver or a barrier. It was considered neither a driver nor a barrier when the number of articles in which the item was identified as a driver was the same as the number of articles in which it was identified as a barrier.¹³ We considered the “level of evidence” to be “very high” if the number of articles in which the specific item was “relevant” was above 12, “high” if this number was between 9 and 12, “medium” if it was either 7 or 8, “low” if it was between 4 and 6 and “very low” if it was lower than 4.

Finally, the level of “agreement” reflects the degree to which the previous literature has reached agreement (or not) on some factors being either drivers or barriers (or neutral) for acceptance. We counted the number of articles in which the item was positively (driver) or negatively (barrier) related to CCUS acceptance. For those articles in which

¹³ Note that causality cannot be assumed in a statistical sense, since an overwhelming majority of papers either used descriptive statistics or cross-section data. Therefore, factors could at best be “associated” to a higher or lower level of social acceptance. However, we believe that, at least theoretically, it can be assumed that the causality goes from the driver/barrier factor to social acceptance and not the other way around. Therefore, we have maintained the terms “direction”, “driver” and “barrier”.

Table 2
List and description of factors influencing the acceptance of CCUS.

Factor	Brief description
SOCIODEMOGRAPHICS	
Age	Age of the respondent
Gender (male)	Gender of the respondent (male or female)
Income	Income level of the respondent
Education	Level of education of the respondent
PROXIMITY, PLACE OF RESIDENCE AND LOCAL ACCEPTANCE	
Proximity	Whether the respondent lives close to a CCUS facility.
BENEFIT PERCEPTION	
Benefit perception	Whether the respondent perceives that CCUS provides benefits to society (whether economic or environmental) or not.
IDEOLOGY, WORLDVIEW, CLIMATE CHANGE AWARENESS, ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS	
Climate change awareness	Whether the respondent is aware of climate change, i. e., whether he/she believes it is an important challenge for humanity.
Political ideology	Where the respondent places himself/herself in the political spectrum (from left to right).
Self-efficacy	This refers to a person's self-assessment of how well he/she generally gets along with technology and how confident he/she is in solving technical problems [55]
Positive emotions	Individuals' emotions can be either positive (e.g., happiness) or negative (e.g., anger). Some authors seek to evaluate individuals' emotions regarding CCS in order to understand the role of emotions [56,57]
AWARENESS/KNOWLEDGE OF CCUS	
CCUS knowledge	Whether the respondent knows CCUS and the level of such knowledge (e.g., whether he/she has only heard of CCUS or actually knows how CCUS works)
CONTRIBUTION TO CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION	
Climate change mitigation	Whether CCUS is considered an effective technology to mitigate climate change
Mitigation deterrence	Whether CCUS is considered to delay investments in other low-carbon technologies (i.e., renewable energy or energy efficiency).
Bridging technology	Whether CCUS is seen as a technology which allows decarbonising the electricity and hard-to-abate sectors, as crucial but expensive alternatives for the energy transition (e.g., hydrogen and storage) experience cost reductions
PERCEPTION OF TECHNOECONOMIC FEATURES OF CCUS	
Costs of CCUS	Whether the costs of CCUS are seen as a barrier or driver to its acceptance.
Maturity	Views on the level of maturity of the technology as a driver or barrier to its acceptance
Perceived innovativeness	Perceived innovativeness of CCUS (high or low)
ENVIRONMENTAL AND SECURITY OF SUPPLY BENEFITS	
Environmental benefits	Whether CCUS is believed to lead to lower environmental impacts
Reduction of fossil fuel dependence	Whether CCUS is believed to reduce fossil fuel dependence
Groundwater pollution	Whether CCUS is believed to increase groundwater pollution
Leakage	Whether CCUS is believed to lead to risks of carbon leakage from storage facilities and pipelines.
Health/environmental risks	Whether CCUS is believed to lead to health and environmental risks.
Environmental effects	Whether CCUS is believed to lead to negative environmental effects
TRUST	
Trust in general	How respondents trust industry and government
Trust in government	How respondents trust the government
Trust in industry	How respondents trust company decision makers involved in the development of CCUS projects
INFORMATION PROVISION	
Information provision	Whether information on CCUS is provided to respondents
Trust in information	Whether the source of the information provided to respondents is considered reliable.
RISK/SAFETY PERCEPTION	
Risks perception	Whether the respondent perceives that CCUS involves risks.
Safety concerns	How concerned the respondents are about the safety of CCUS.

Source: Own elaboration.

Table 3
Evaluation criteria and their thresholds.

Scale	Level of relevance (LR)(%)	Direction	Level of evidence (LE)	Level of agreement (LA)
Very low (VL)	LR < 20	A positive sign is indicative of a "driver" of CCUS acceptance, whereas a negative direction indicates a "barrier".	LE < 4	Same (D) and (B) answers
Low (L)	20 ≤ LR < 40		4 ≤ LE < 7	1 or 2 more (D/B) answers than (B/D) answers.
Medium (M)	40 ≤ LR < 60		7 ≤ LE < 9	3 or 4 more (D/B) answers than (B/D) answers.
High (H)	60 ≤ LR < 80		9 ≤ LE < 12	5 or 6 more (D/B) answers than (B/D) answers
Very high (VH)	≥80		LE ≥ 12	More than 6 (D/B) answers than (B/D) answers

Source: Own elaboration. Note: D = driver, B = barrier.

the specific item was "relevant", the level of agreement was calculated as the difference between the number of articles in which it was a driver and those in which it was a barrier. We deemed agreement on a specific factor to be "very high" when a substantially greater number of studies identified the factor as a driver compared to the studies that identified it as a barrier. Agreement was "very low" when the same number of studies identified a factor as a driver and as a barrier (Table 3).

An example would help to illustrate the above discussion, using the factor "proximity", i.e. whether being closer to the CCUS facility leads to higher or lower acceptance levels (NIMBY). This factor is mentioned in 19 articles. In 17 of them, it is a "relevant" factor. Therefore, the percentage of "relevance" is 17/19 = 89% (very high relevance). Then, the factor is negatively related to acceptance in 16 articles and positively related in only one article. Therefore, the factor could be considered a "barrier". Since this factor is relevant in many articles, the degree of evidence is very high. Finally, it is a barrier rather than a driver in an overwhelming majority of articles and, thus, the level of agreement is very high. Nevertheless, caution should be taken when using this indicator of "relevance" as it does not consider the share of articles (within the final list of articles included in the review) which actually investigated the specific factor, possibly leading to inflated relevance scores. In other words, the relevance of a given factor can be high because it has been included in the reviewed papers more than other factors, but still be low in the sense that relatively few articles include it.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Descriptive results

Information on the temporal and geographical scope, sub-technology focus, acceptance focus, aim, approach, method and number of citations of the selected 84 articles is provided in Appendices 3 and 4. As in other reviews in the energy policy realm, Figs. 2–6 provide basic descriptive information (see also the figures in Appendix 5).

Four journals account for 46% of the articles reviewed, whereas 17 journals only have one contribution. There is not a clear time trend, although there are relatively few studies in the most recent years (from 2020). The geographical coverage of the publications is diverse, but some degree of concentration exists. Around a third of the studies refer to Germany, the U.S. and the Netherlands. Most research has focused on

Fig. 2. Number of studies per journal.

* The category “others” refers to journals with only one paper included in this review: Applied Energy, Australian Journal of Emerging Technologies and Society, Climatic Change, Energies, Energy, Environmental Science and Policy, Frontiers in Energy Research, Human and Ecological Risk Assessment, Journal of Cleaner Production, Journal of Risk Research, Mitigation and Adaption Strategies for Global Change, Nature Climate Change, Oil and Gas Science and Technology, Procedia Economics and Finance, Palgrave Communications, Science and Public Policy and Sustainable Production and Consumption. See Appendix 6 for an analysis of the quality of each journal based on impact factors and category rankings.

Fig. 3. Year of publication of the selected articles (number of articles).

Source. Own elaboration. Notes: All items are counted individually, i.e., if an article focuses on two countries, the two countries are counted. There are two studies which investigate a period of two years. In those cases, the first year is shown. A few studies provide two separate snapshots in time (non-consecutive years). In those cases, both years are shown.

developed countries. General CCUS acceptance is the most studied (46 studies), followed by a national (29) and local (27) scope. The capture and storage stages have attracted most research attention (62 studies for CCS as well as 3 for geological and 2 for unspecified storage), whereas “utilisation” has received much less attention. Most data have been gathered through online surveys (48 studies), followed by paper-and-pencil surveys (13). The range of sample sizes is very wide (between 60 and 13901 respondents). The same percentage of studies (around 43%) have sample sizes below 700 respondents and between 700 and

2000 respondents. A few surveys have more than 2000 participants. The collected data were mostly analysed with descriptive statistics (37 studies) and different types of econometric analyses (39).

The following subsections discuss the results of the review regarding the acceptance of CCUS technologies (3.2) and the drivers and barriers of such acceptance (3.3).

Fig. 4. Geographical distribution.
 Not shown with legend/data in the figure: Brazil, Denmark, France, Greece, Indonesia, Korea, Romania, Taiwan and Turkey (each has one study).

Fig. 5. Acceptance focus.

3.2. Acceptance of CCUS technologies

An analysis of the studies reviewed allows us to infer some conclusions regarding the level of acceptance of CCUS (see also [Appendix 7](#)).

3.2.1. General acceptance of CCUS

The general acceptance of CCUS technologies ranges from neutral to slightly positive, although there are considerable cross-country differences. For example, the perceptions regarding the use of CCUS

technologies in the six countries analysed in [58] ranged from a more or less neutral to a slightly positive assessment. [59] also revealed that support for CCUS was greatest in the UK and lowest in the Netherlands. Differences also exist within countries, i.e., between regions in Germany [60].

3.2.2. Relative acceptance of CCUS

CCUS technologies are generally less preferred than other mitigation options. For example, renewable energies were significantly more

Fig. 6. Number of articles focusing on each stage of CCUS.

preferred over CCS in [61] and in [52]. In [62], CCS ranked 8 out of 12 for Australia, and 10 out of 12 in China when participants were asked to rank the energy sources and mitigation technologies. In [63], CCS was evaluated negatively by most respondents, whereas most other options were assessed positively. [64,65] found that support for CCS was much lower than for other mitigation technologies. Some studies found evidence that CCUS technologies were more supported when used in combination with other technologies [66,67].

3.2.3. Spatial responsiveness in CCUS acceptance

There is strong evidence of “NIMBY” effects. For example, in [68], over 80% of respondents from the state of Indiana in the US expressed support for the general use of CCS, but 20% of these initial supporters exhibited a NIMBY-like reaction and switched to opposition as a CCS facility was proposed close to their communities. [69] found that, in Canada, 61% of respondents opposed or strongly opposed a CCS project being constructed within 25 km of their homes, whereas only 8.9% supported or strongly supported it. [61] found a NIMBY phenomenon in China, which was related to transportation and storage, similar to Ref. [70]. In [71], local acceptance levels in Germany were lower when either a CCS or a CCU site was proposed nearby. In [72], CO₂ pipelines near respondents' homes were generally less acceptable in Switzerland than those further away. In [73], less people opposed the implementation of “CCS offshore at tens of kilometers off the coast near Japan” compared to “CCS offshore at a few kilometers away from the closest shore to their house”. In [74], CO₂-storage in general was positively rated by residents in Alkmaar and Bergen (The Netherlands) (average of 3.17 on a 5 point scale). However, acceptance decreased significantly when they were asked what would be their score if storage was located near their residential areas (2.59). A few articles reported evidence of NIMBY not being problematic [75,76], or people even being in favour of the location of a CCUS project nearby [59].

A note of caution on the NIMBY phenomenon is needed here, since it has been criticised for being simplistic, as spatial effects are known to depend strongly on measurement approaches and contextual factors. For example, [69, p.431] argues that the NIMBY concept has been used as an explanation for opposition that is determined at the individual level by ignorance, irrationality and selfishness, under the assumption that opposition is based upon a lack of knowledge of the technology (the ‘information deficit’). [77] observes that individuals opposing developments are often highly informed and cannot be considered ignorant and that the self-interest explanation is based upon rational choice presumptions that overlook the importance of issues of justice, equity and trust in energy conflicts. In a review of the spatial dimensions

of stated preference valuation techniques. [78] has argued that preferences and WTP often vary over space and that spatial patterns are complex and often defy modelling using simple, unidirectional distance-based analysis that overlooks confounding factors. “Space matters”, but how it matters (specifically) and the most effective ways to model spatial dimensions remain topics of continued research. More specifically for CCS, [79] argues that identifying the place factors that have played a role in the development of CCS provides a basis to understand how place shapes public reactions in relation to CCS projects. On the other hand, acceptance of location-specific CCS can be influenced by information and question framing. [80] finds that question order significantly impacts the acceptance of CCS locations and that CCS familiarity correlates positively and significantly with the acceptance of some types of CCS (offshore CCS, nearshore CCS and onshore rural CCS).

3.3. Drivers and barriers of CCUS acceptance

The results of the analysis for each individual factor in each evaluation criterion are summarised in Table 4.

Regarding the different dimensions of social acceptance, most factors are highly relevant as drivers or barriers for CCUS acceptance. Only some sociodemographic factors (“age”, “gender” and “income”), as well as “CCUS awareness” and “costs”, have low to medium scores on the relevance index. In contrast, there is a low or medium level of evidence and agreement for many factors. Apart from “sociodemographics”, “proximity”, “benefit perception” and “CCUS knowledge”, those levels are not high for the categories “Ideology, worldview, climate change awareness, environmental awareness” (except for the specific factor “climate change awareness”), “contribution to climate change mitigation” (except for “climate change mitigation”), “perception of technoeconomic features of CCUS”, “environmental and security of supply benefits” (except for “leakage”), “trust” (except for “trust in general”) and “information provision” and “risk/safety perception” (except for “risk perception”).

Most relevant factors are drivers of acceptance, but some are barriers (“proximity”, “mitigation deterrence”, “maturity and costs of CCUS”, “leakage”, “health/environmental risks”, “environmental effects”, “risks perception” and “safety concerns”). Both the level of agreement and evidence are high for all the relevant factors included in four categories (“sociodemographics”, “proximity”, “place of residence and local acceptance”, “benefit perception” and “awareness/knowledge of CCUS”), whereas it is mixed for factors included in the other broad categories (“ideology”, “contribution to climate change mitigation”, “perception of technoeconomic features”, “environmental benefits”,

Table 4
Score of each factor in each dimension of social acceptance by thematic categories.

Factor	Relevance			Relv. (4)	Direction			Evidence (8) ^b	Agreement (9) ^c
	Relv. (1)	Not relv. (2)	% relv. (3)		Driver (5)	Barrier (6)	Net (7) ^a		
SOCIODEMOGRAPHICS									
Age	11	21	34	L	7	4	D	H	M
Gender (male)	19	18	51	M	13	6	D	VH	VH
Income	12	13	48	M	9	3	D	VH	H
Education	11	23	32	L	9	2	D	H	VH
PROXIMITY AND LOCAL ACCEPTANCE									
Proximity	17	2	89	VH	1	16	B	VH	VH
BENEFIT PERCEPTION									
Benefit perception	23	2	92	VH	23	0	D	VH	VH
IDEOLOGY, WORLDVIEWS, CLIMATE CHANGE AWARENESS AND ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS									
Climate change awareness	23	9	72	H	20	3	D	VH	VH
Political ideology	7	4	64	H	4	3	D	M	L
Self-efficacy	2	0	100	VH	2	0	D(u)	VL	L
Positive emotions	4	2	67	H	4	0	D	L	M
AWARENESS / KNOWLEDGE OF CCS									
CCS knowledge	17	12	59	M	15	2	D	VH	VH
CONTRIBUTION TO CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION									
Climate change mitigation	18	3	86	VH	16	2	D	VH	VH
Mitigation deterrence	4	0	100	VH	0	4	B	L	M
Bridging technology	2	0	100	VH	2	0	D(u)	L	L
PERCEPTION OF TECHNOECONOMIC FEATURES OF CCS									
Costs of CCS	4	3	57	M	0	4	B	M	M
Maturity	4	0	100	VH	1	3	B(u)	L	L
Perceived innovativeness	2	0	100	VH	2	0	D(u)	VL	L
ENVIRONMENTAL AND SECURITY OF SUPPLY BENEFITS									
Environmental benefits	8	1	89	VH	8	0	D	M	VH
Reduction of fossil fuel dependence	3	0	100	VH	3	0	D	VL	M
Groundwater pollution	3	0	100	VH	1	2	B(u)	VL	L
Leakage	11	0	100	VH	0	11	B	H	VH
Health and environmental risks	2	0	100	VH	0	2	B(u)	VL	L
Negative environmental effects	4	1	80	VH	0	4	B	L	M
TRUST									
Trust in general	10	1	91	VH	10	0	D	H	VH
Trust in government	6	1	86	VH	5	1	D	L	M
Trust in industry	4	1	80	VH	4	0	D	L	M
INFORMATION PROVISION									
Information provision	19	2	90	VH	11	8	D	H	M
Trust in information	2	0	100	VH	2	0	D(u)	VL	L
RISK/SAFETY PERCEPTION									
Risk perception	24	5	83	VH	1	23	B	VH	VH
Safety concerns	4	0	100	VH	0	4	B	M	

^a D = Driver; B = Barrier; u = Uncertain (when the difference between the number of articles for a given factor in which it is a driver (barrier) exceeds the number of articles in which it is a barrier (driver) is very small, i.e. only one or two articles).

^b See column (1).

^c See columns (6) and (7).

“security of supply benefits”, “trust”, “information provision” and “risk and safety perception”). Overall, only a few drivers and barriers have high to very high scores in the three dimensions, indicating a rather nuanced picture. This is the case for “proximity”, “leakage” and “risk perception” regarding barriers and “benefit perception”, “climate change awareness”, “climate change mitigation” and “trust” regarding drivers.

An overall ranking for the dimensions “relevance”, “agreement” and “evidence” using one composite indicator for the drivers and barriers has been built (see Appendix 8). The drivers with the highest overall score in the ranking are “climate change mitigation” and “benefit perception”, followed by “trust in general” and “climate change awareness”. The barriers with the highest overall score in the ranking are “proximity” and “risk perception”, followed by “leakage”. Given that the dimensions of relevance, agreement and evidence refer to different aspects, the interpretation of this overall ranking has to be treated with caution.

3.3.1. Relevant barriers

The relevant barriers can be grouped in four categories.

3.3.1.1. Perceived risks of CCUS.

These include perceived

environmental risks in general, and the risks of carbon leakage in particular. They also refer to health risks and safety concerns about the facilities. They are all very relevant barriers to CCUS but, except for leakage and risk perception, the evidence and level of agreement are not high.

3.3.1.2. Proximity to CCUS. Being close to a CCUS facility reduces the acceptance of CCUS. This finding is very robust, since both the relevance, evidence and level of agreement for this factor are very high. The NIMBY for CCUS has received substantial attention in the literature since the early works on CCUS acceptance, although it has also been criticised, given the complexity of spatial responsiveness in acceptance formation (see section 3.2), which make us being cautious when interpreting the negative effects of proximity. NIMBY suggests that people are not necessarily against CCUS and may value its contribution to climate change mitigation. They may even favour CCUS facilities in their country, but they do not want to live close to them, given their potential environmental and health risks.

3.3.1.3. Mitigation deterrence vs. bridging technology. These factors, which are found to be very relevant, have a high level of agreement as a barrier (mitigation deterrence) or as a driver (bridging technology) to

CCUS acceptance. However, the level of evidence is low. Many believe that CCUS contributes to carbon lock-in, i.e., the continuation of the use of fossil fuels. In their view, CCUS deters other mitigation options in the fight against climate change (i.e., renewable energy technologies), leading to a low acceptance for CCUS. However, some people would like CCUS to be a bridging technology that would allow near-term reductions in GHG emissions while long-term alternatives are developed [67].

3.3.1.4. Techno-economic features. The relatively lower maturity and higher costs of CCUS make it unattractive for the general public compared to other mitigation alternatives. In contrast, the innovative character of CCUS is regarded as a driver. Notwithstanding, the level of evidence and agreement are low to medium for all these factors. Regarding costs, four articles find that they negatively influence acceptance [67,81–83], but this factor is not relevant in three articles [59,84,85].

3.3.2. Relevant drivers

Regarding the drivers, four sets of categories can also be identified.

3.3.2.1. Environmental benefits. Environmental benefits seem to be a double-edge sword. As mentioned above, environmental risks represent a relevant barrier to CCUS acceptance. However, the general public believe that CCUS can be effective for climate change mitigation. This factor is very relevant and also has very high levels of evidence and agreement. The fact that climate change concern is a relevant driver of CCUS acceptance (with a very high level of evidence and agreement), and that CCUS is considered to be a useful mitigation technology, confirm this interpretation. This result may suggest a trade-off between the local and global environmental impacts of CCUS regarding their influence on acceptance. Whereas the former is seen as a barrier, the second is a driver.

3.3.2.2. Benefit perception. Benefit perception is not only related to the environmental benefits, but also to the socioeconomic ones, e.g. job creation. Benefit perception is a very relevant factor, and also has a very high level of evidence and agreement. The reduction in foreign fossil fuel dependence is considered a very relevant benefit in this context, although with a very low evidence and medium level of agreement.

3.3.2.3. Knowledge and information. The levels of knowledge on CCUS are generally low among the general public [58,86–88], particularly when compared to other mitigation technologies [62,64] (see also [Appendix 9](#)). Our review shows that CCUS knowledge is a driver of acceptance, with medium levels of relevance but very high levels of evidence and agreement.¹⁴ This suggests that people who know CCUS value more its benefits (in terms of climate mitigation or national/local socioeconomic benefits) than its risks (to the environment or human health). The fact that information provision is a highly relevant factor (with a very high evidence, although medium levels of agreement) reinforces the interpretation that the more the people know about CCUS, the more acceptable it is.¹⁵ However, as mentioned above, it is not only

¹⁴ Since people can only reflect on their acceptance for something (i.e., CCUS) when they know about it, and as CCUS has been in an early stage of deployment, it could be expected that relatively few respondents had heard of it prior to the survey. Consequently, in order to facilitate informed acceptance statements, the respondents in the surveys are given information on CCUS and, thus, even those who do not know it can state whether they support it or not.

¹⁵ However, this relationship between knowledge/information and acceptance is not a perfect one, as suggested by the medium levels of relevance of CCUS knowledge and the medium level of agreement of information provision. Indeed, [89] have conducted a review on the effect of information on individuals' perception of CCS. Seven studies found negative information effects, whereas twelve studies found positive effects.

an issue of how much information is provided, but CCUS acceptance is likely to depend on information and question framing [80] and the effectiveness of information dissemination channels [90–94]. This last topic is further addressed below (see 3.3.2.4 and 5.2.4).

3.3.2.4. Trust. Trust in information is a very relevant driver (although with a very low level of evidence and agreement). This indicates that the source of information (i.e., the messenger) is a relevant driver of acceptance. Indeed, the criticism of the “Deficit Model” in climate psychology points out that simply increasing knowledge does not necessarily enhance acceptance unless accompanied by a high degree of trust. Thus, knowledge may be moderated by the level of trust. Trust plays a mediating effect between benefit perception and risk perception of CCUS and CCUS acceptance in [92,95,96]. [95] found moderating effects of trust on the relationship between perceived risks and benefits and acceptance. [92] showed that scientific and technological trust significantly impacted CCS acceptance when basic information was provided. In a paper specifically devoted to the analysis of the influence of trust on CCUS acceptance. [96] showed that, when the less trusted industrial stakeholder communicated the environmental benefits of CCS, this activated less trust than when the more trusted environmental NGO communicated those benefits.¹⁶ However, the influence of trust on acceptance may be moderated by some factors, i.e. in [57,74] it influenced perceived benefits and risks through the positive and negative emotions that could be generated. In [92], trust indirectly impacted the acceptance of CCS through benefit perception, risk perception, recognition of utility and NIMBY.

Trust on government and industry is also a very relevant driver of acceptance (although with medium or very low levels of evidence and medium levels of agreement in the last two cases). In line with the procedural justice argument discussed in the Just Energy Transition literature [97], public participation mechanisms would enhance trust and, thus, CCUS acceptance, as shown in [28,98] (see also 5.2.8).¹⁷

3.4. Sensitivity analysis

As mentioned before, the threshold values were defined based on the outcome of the SR. In order to validate the robustness of the results, a sensitivity analysis was performed. It was assessed whether changes in the threshold values significantly altered the outcome. Therefore, these were adjusted as follows: For “LR”, the threshold values were adjusted by a 10% reduction and a 10% increase; for “LE”, the threshold values were adjusted by a unit decrease and increase on the number of “relevant” factors, respectively; and for “LA”, the values were adjusted by a unit decrease and increase on the difference value. Therefore, the different variable scales were taken into account. The results of the sensitivity analysis generally confirm the robustness of the results of the SR, as the adjusted values did not lead to major changes in the results. The overall “role” of any given factor did not change significantly in any case. There were only minor changes (see [Appendix 10](#)).

3.5. Contribution of this study/comparison with related CCUS acceptance reviews

Compared to previous reviews, this one provides additional insights, which are related to the systematic, four-dimensional framework quantitatively applied to a low level of granularity of the factors related to the social acceptance of CCUS. It allows us to provide a ranking of

¹⁶ As observed by Yang et al. ([95], p.71), a mediating role of trust on the acceptance of non-CCUS technologies and hazardous activities has been found, including gene technology, radioactive waste disposal and food manufacturing.

¹⁷ [98] focused on public participation as a way to improve information dissemination, whereas [28] analysed public participation mechanisms as a conflict solution method.

specific factors which are positively or negatively related to public acceptance in each of the four dimensions. This is not done in any of the previous reviews, since they either do not provide a ranking of those factors [23,46] or the ranking is based on how many reviewed articles mention the factors [9,22].¹⁸

In [9], most mentioned factors were: “Knowledge”, “acceptance of CCS and preference between technologies”, “governmental policy and interaction between stakeholders” and “benefits and risks perception”. Most mentioned risks were “CO₂ leakage”, “migration (from storage or pipeline) or explosion and disposal of CO₂ may cause seismic activity” and “environmental impact”. Most mentioned barriers were “lack of public knowledge about CCS”, “lack of or poor communication strategy” and “competition between alternative technologies”. The paper count in Ref. [22] shows that “perceived balance of benefits, costs and risks” is the most frequently mentioned factor affecting positive perceptions of CCUS in the reviewed literature, followed by “outcome efficacy”, “trust”, “fairness” and “technology knowledge and awareness”. The most frequently mentioned factor affecting negative perceptions of CCUS in the reviewed literature is “high costs and risks”, followed by “lack of trust, knowledge and awareness” and “NIMBY”.

Compared to the results of [9,22], our review confirms the importance of benefit perception, knowledge of CCUS and trust on relevant stakeholders as important drivers. It further suggests that effectiveness in climate change mitigation is a very important driver. In contrast, our findings show that some barriers (perceived technological risks and leakage) play a more relevant role, whereas others which are more relevant in the other reviews (e.g., high costs and risks” or “lack of trust” in Ref. [22], and “lack of knowledge about CCS” and “competition between alternative technologies” in Ref. [9]) are less relevant in this review. The importance of proximity to a CCUS facility (NIMBY) in our review is in line with both [9,22]. Again, caution should be taken when comparing our results to other reviews, given the different scope and methodological differences.

4. Policy implications

The results of our review suggest that, if policy makers believe that CCUS is worth receiving public support, dedicated measures should be directed to activate the identified drivers or to mitigate the barriers in order to foster the social acceptance of these technologies.

An important result is that a higher level of awareness and knowledge about CCUS is related to a higher level of acceptance of the technology, and also that knowledge about its socioeconomic and environmental benefits is a very relevant driver of acceptance. Therefore, knowledge of CCUS should be increased for the general public and information should be provided on its benefits, particularly with respect to its climate mitigation potentials.

Information provision should stress the role of CCUS in the decarbonised energy transition and the fact that CCUS does not necessarily imply a slowdown in the uptake of other technologies. While mitigation deterrence due to CCUS may be a possibility in the electricity generation sector (although decarbonisation is currently based on renewable energy technologies almost everywhere), CCUS is also regarded by many as a bridging technology. It is also an alternative to decarbonise hard-to-abate industrial sectors. Therefore, emphasising the need to sequester hard-to-abate emissions, which is made possible by CCUS [90,99], could be an effective way to encourage the acceptance of CCUS. Since risks and safety concerns are very relevant barriers to CCUS acceptance, information on technology-inherent risks (notably leakage), and how they are addressed, should transparently be provided to the general public.

¹⁸ In these last two reviews, the ranking is proposed without considering if the factor is positively or negatively related to public acceptance [9] or considering that the factor is positively, neutrally or negatively related to public acceptance without analysing the “net effect” [22].

However, some authors have stressed that information provision does not necessarily result in higher acceptance levels. When receiving more information, perceived uncertainty can also lead to negative attitudes [90,91,100]. The rejection of people that only have a rudimentary knowledge is based on affective evaluations related to (dis)trust [51]. How the information is provided and the trust on who provides it make a difference in this context.¹⁹ The high relevance of trust in information as a driver of acceptance in our review suggests that both the information itself as well as the “messenger” should be perceived as trustworthy.

The public is not a homogeneous group, and the risks associated with the different stages of CCUS may be perceived differently by different groups [51]. Thus, policy makers and project developers need first to identify possible target groups and determine the information needed for the respective groups and how to convey it. Our review shows that demographic factors (income, gender and age) influence CCUS acceptance (albeit with a low to medium level of relevance). Therefore, as suggested by Ref. [92], tailored promotion and educational activities should be designed for different demographic groups.

Then, it should be assessed on which distribution channels the information must be made available to the public [91]. Specialised government agencies, i.e., environmental or energy agencies, can play an important role in information provision. They may publicise successful cases of CCUS technology to increase public confidence in the technology [92]. [90] shows that people prefer receiving information via traditional channels rather than social media, and several papers show that scientists are the most trusted source to inform about CCUS, followed by public authorities and environmental associations (NGOs) [50, 90,96,101,102] (see 5.2.4).

The negative impact of proximity found in our review, combined with the insights of the critical NIMBY literature on the role of place attachment and place identity to explain local opposition [77,103], suggest that, in addition to clearly and transparently informing about the benefits and risks of CCUS, specifically for the local population, policy makers could play an important role to reduce local opposition by engaging in dialogue with local communities. Measures related to *procedural sustainability* should be adopted. The willingness of people to accept low-carbon technology projects in their community depends on whether the project decision-making process is regarded as fair. Perceived procedural fairness generally increases project acceptance of low-carbon technology projects by local communities [104]. Thus, the public should be engaged in the development and implementation of CCUS technology. The government can organise public participation in the planning and decision-making processes of CCUS projects, including consultations and public hearings, to take into account the concerns and interests of the public. This would build trust and confidence in this technology [92,105].

Arguably, providing monetary compensation to affected citizens due to the potentially negative effects of nearby CCUS facilities may reduce local opposition and increase local acceptance. However, this role of monetary compensation to increase acceptance has not been analysed in a systematic manner. Whereas it could enhance acceptance, there might also be some rejection since it could be regarded as a “buying of consciences” [106].

5. Knowledge gaps and future research directions

This systematic review allows us to identify gaps in knowledge and make suggestions for future research. They have been grouped in 17 items corresponding to 3 broad categories.

¹⁹ As put by Ref. [50], the acceptance of laypersons without a deep technical knowledge is mediated by the trust in the information, the technology and the information provider.

5.1. CCUS acceptance focus

5.1.1. Acceptance of different stages, alternatives and technologies

The vast majority of studies either treat CCUS technologies as one block of technologies or focus uniquely on storage. Few contributions assess acceptance levels across the different CCUS stages. Future research should cover this gap in knowledge. These studies identify significant differences. Storage has been found to influence acceptance more than the other steps (e.g., [71,107]). The transportation and utilisation stages have received traditionally less attention in the past, although some analyses have recently been performed; e.g., [51] for CO₂-based jet fuels, [108] for CO₂-based products such as fuels and food, or [91] for CCU products such as clothing, cosmetics and food packaging.

Our review suggests that there might be important differences regarding CCUS acceptance across alternatives (e.g., CCS vs CCU, transport options²⁰, onshore vs offshore storage and the origin of the CO₂ to be stored, i.e. whether it is imported or comes from domestic sources). However, these issues have either received limited attention or the evidence is not conclusive, and represent important research gaps which should be addressed in the future.

In particular, although the capture element of CCS and CCU is common to both of them, they have different features with respect to how the carbon is disposed or used which likely influence their acceptance.²¹ However, despite recent efforts, not much focus has been put on their comparative acceptance. Those which have carried out such assessment show that CCU is more acceptable than CCS [71,105,110]. [109] suggest that support for CCU may be greater than for CCS in part because “climate skeptics can get excited about the co-benefits of CCU even if they don't see any value in reducing greenhouse gas emissions” [109, p.323]. Acceptance of CCU has clearly been much less studied than CCS in the literature (see Fig. 6), although some recent articles have focused on CCU [51,103,108,109].

Regarding CO₂ transport options, the level of CCS acceptance decreased significantly in a German national sample when CO₂ transport through a pipeline was made explicit [52]. Nevertheless, in another study for Germany, the level of CCS acceptance did not change as a function of pipeline transport [60].

The results on preferences for off-shore versus onshore storage are mixed, with all kinds of evidence regarding one choice versus the other: in favour, against and neutral. [60] found that, nationwide, offshore storage was preferred over on-shore storage in Germany. However, respondents from the coastal regions preferred on-shore storage. In [111], respondents had positive acceptance levels about diverse storage options, including ocean, lake, geological on-shore and geological offshore options, but this was not the case for the ocean-dilution-type option. Similar results could be found in their earlier study [112], with respondents being more opposed to ocean-dilution-type storage than other options. In that study, the general public were most likely to favour offshore storage. However, more than half of the respondents in [113] had a neutral view regarding the implementation of on-shore versus offshore geological storage. In another study, respondents from Norway and Germany did not evaluate offshore and on-shore storage differently [88].

There is a low level of evidence in the literature regarding the acceptance of different sources of the CO₂ being captured. A notable

exception is [52], which showed that the CO₂ captured from coal power plants was much less acceptable than the CO₂ from biomass or industry. [107,114] focused on the acceptance of two alternatives: bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) and Direct Air Capture (DAC). Whereas [107] found that BECCS was preferred over DAC, [114] did not find any differences between the acceptance levels of both options.

Only two studies focus on acceptance of foreign sourced vs. domestically sourced CO₂. In their analysis of Norway and Germany, [88] found that “Norwegian respondents evaluate a project where foreign sourced CO₂ is stored in Norway substantially more negatively compared to a project where domestically sourced CO₂ is stored in Norway. By contrast, German respondents are not affected by the variation of the nationality of emissions or the storage site” [88, p.1]. [90] showed that participants supported CO₂ storage in Switzerland the most when the CO₂ came from Switzerland, followed by neighbouring countries or Europe. Storage was not supported when the CO₂ originates from outside Europe or its origin was unknown.

An important issue is the acceptance of DACCs and BECCs compared to CCUS in general. DACCs allows the use of renewable energy to power direct air capture of CO₂ [115].²² BECCS allows the generation of negative emissions, which is critical to comply with long-term mitigation targets [6,116]. The biogenic feature and future role of BECCS would probably lead to a higher degree of social acceptance than CCS for fossil fuel-based energy production, as found in Refs. [52,59]. However, this topic has received scant attention and merits further research.

5.1.2. iCCS vs. CCS for electricity generation

Compared to the use of CCS for coal-fired power plants, there is now a greater focus on “hard-to-abate” industrial emissions [99]. CCS can directly capture and store CO₂ emissions from large industrial facilities. Thus, industrial CCS (iCCS) can play a crucial role to provide deep emissions reductions in sectors where renewable energy is less effective for this purpose [92]. It is the only technology which is considered to be able to directly decarbonise those industrial facilities without requiring a complete rethinking of the industrial sectors [101]. However, previous quantitative research has focused on the acceptance of CCS in general, instead of iCCS in particular [99]. For local acceptance, it may not be the same if a CCUS facility was added to keep a coal power plant in operation, safeguarding national electricity supply under fluctuating renewables (local risks, national benefits), that if a CCUS facility was added to keep a local industry that is hard to decarbonise in operation (local risks, local benefits). The possible different attitude of society (whether national or local) towards iCCS versus CCS for electricity generation should be further explored. Indeed, [99] show relatively high public acceptance for iCCS. Similarly, [90] show that, when respondents were mentioned the need to sequester hard-to-abate emissions, opinion shifted towards support. Future research on public acceptance under the decarbonisation needs of industrial sectors in developing countries should be carried out.

5.1.3. General vs. local acceptance

General acceptance for CCUS (i.e., whether an individual supports the concept of CCUS) can be expected to be higher than the acceptance of a CCUS facility in the immediate neighborhood (local acceptance), simplified as the NIMBY effect [71]. Further research should focus on the differential reasons for both types of acceptance and, particularly, on the role of trust, place attachment or local identity in this context [103].

5.1.4. Bridging technology vs. deterrence (lock-in)

As shown before, two views on the role of CCUS in a decarbonised energy transition have opposing influences on its acceptance (mitigation

²⁰ For example, for off-shore storage, it would be interesting to identify whether CO₂ transport by pipeline or ship would be more socially acceptable.

²¹ [109] provide an extensive discussion of these differences. Compared to CCS, acceptance of CCU is higher, as people perceive it to be less risky. Concerns about CCS are mostly related to potential CO₂ leakage during transportation or storage. Instead, acceptance of CCU is more strongly related to beliefs about product usage and disposal [71], although questions of where to locate facilities and the potential for leakage are still relevant [109].

²² According to Ref. [115], DACCs may lead to both negative responses (e.g., due to injection deep underground) and positive ones (e.g., due to use of renewables to power direct air capture of CO₂).

deterrence vs. bridging technology). Our review shows that only a few papers include one of those two perspectives but, to our knowledge, there isn't any paper which includes both views in their survey. Therefore, more research on this topic is needed, identifying which perspective dominates and (through a mediation analysis) which characteristics of the individuals make them more likely to support one perspective or the other.

5.2. Drivers and barriers to acceptance

5.2.1. The need for a transdisciplinary theoretical framework

Several approaches have been followed to analyse CCUS acceptance, including sociology, psychology, and economics. However, a more sophisticated, transdisciplinary theoretical framework is missing in the literature. This should include cognitive elements, but also other aspects (such as the economic ones), which influence acceptance issues, in line with the integrated approach developed by [27]. As argued by Ref. [92], enhancing public acceptance of CCUS technology is a complex issue that requires a multidisciplinary approach and interdisciplinary cooperation.

5.2.2. A focus on already implemented projects

The surveys on CCUS acceptance ask respondents to assess CCUS in general or CCUS projects which may eventually be deployed in their vicinity. Further research efforts should be devoted to the analysis of the acceptance (by both the local and national population) of projects which have already been implemented, comparing those ex-post assessments with expectations before their implementation. This may provide valuable information for policy makers to enhance the acceptance of future projects.

5.2.3. Some drivers and barriers have been under-researched

Our review provides limited or ambiguous evidence regarding the impact on social acceptance of some factors, such as ideology, world-views and sociodemographic features (age, race, gender and income). Therefore, future research should focus on the analysis of these factors.

5.2.4. Drivers and barriers related to the communicator and channels of communication (communication products)

The low level of CCUS awareness makes it recommendable to provide background information to respondents about the technologies. Therefore, beliefs and opinions about the technologies are likely to be influenced by how these are described, i.e. by factors related to the communicator and the methods and channels of communication [93, 94]. The existing evidence clearly supports the idea that scientists and NGOs are the most trusted communicators, positively influencing acceptance, followed by governments, with industries being the least trusted ([50,90,96,101,102]). In contrast, the influence of new types of communication on CCUS acceptance (i.e., social media) versus traditional media has not been analysed in the literature. The only exception is [90], which showed that people preferred receiving information via reports on TV, short explanatory videos and newspaper articles, whereas social media posts and podcasts were the least preferred channels. Thus, further research should explore the impact of different types of information sources on CCUS acceptance.²³ As put by [90] best practices and guidelines are missing on how to design these communication products so that people with different abilities and preferences understand the information. Finally, there is not much research specifically on the interaction between trust and information provision or trust and knowledge (see 3.3.2.4), and issue which should be further investigated.

²³ An important, and emerging topic in this context is the effect of current greenwashing cases, which can decrease CCUS acceptance by negatively affecting trust [90]. Further research on this topic is needed.

5.2.5. Mediating effects in the analysis of drivers and barriers

Drivers and barriers may interact with each other, i.e. a specific factor may have a direct and an indirect effect on CCUS acceptance. For example, NIMBY directly influences acceptance of CCUS, whereas trust significantly influences such acceptance through the impact on NIMBY (e.g., [92]). Trust can affect acceptance either directly, or through perceived risks and benefits (e.g., [101]). In this review, we included the most relevant drivers and barriers which may either directly or indirectly influence acceptance, but we have not systematically investigated the mediating or moderating effects of the variables that may influence the relationship between a given factor and acceptance. This should be the focus of future research. An analytical and methodological framework should be developed to systematically assess the outcomes of mediation or moderation analyses of the drivers and barriers to CCUS acceptance, distinguishing between direct and indirect effects.

5.2.6. How to deal with pseudo opinions?

Pseudo opinions represent a critical issue when assessing the acceptance of CCUS. A general finding of our review is that the level of awareness of CCUS is very low. Many people do not know anything about the technology when asked about their acceptance. However, these respondents without prior knowledge of the technology still state what is referred to as "non-opinions" or "pseudo-opinions" [99]. Only [99] has assessed this issue in depth, arguing that the assumption that respondents without stated prior knowledge state pseudo-opinions should be revised, and that those respondents should be assumed to state spontaneous opinions. However, it is still an open issue whether those opinions should be considered when assessing acceptance [51], and further research should be carried out on this topic.

5.2.7. The role of costs

Our analysis suggests that the impact of techno-economic features on CCUS acceptance has received limited attention. More specifically, the influence of costs on the social acceptance of CCUS has been addressed in a limited manner. First, the issue of how costs influence acceptance has been less addressed in the literature compared to other determinants. Second, costs have been included in an inconsistent manner across those studies, with different definitions, e.g. CO₂ abatement costs [67], lower costs than alternative abatement technologies [117], higher costs of CCUS deployment [59,118], higher monthly costs per household [82], higher electricity bills [67], higher energy prices [84] and whether CCUS will become more economically viable [81].²⁴

5.2.8. Assessing trade-offs

There might be trade-offs in the assessment of CCUS acceptance. For example, [109] suggests that the U.S. public may perceive environmental trade-offs, with CCU's climate benefits possibly coming at the expense of other environmental outcomes such as land use changes for CCU infrastructure or local air pollution caused by leaked CO₂. In the formation of acceptance, consumers usually make trade-offs between different product properties. The literature does not address the trade-offs between higher costs and other impacts (with the exception of [67]). This is a particularly serious omission, since it would be interesting to know whether a higher cost combined with the social and environmental benefits that CCUS brings is acceptable, and how the higher costs and those other benefits trade-off between each other. As suggested by [91], which properties are important in this context and how they are weighted should be investigated. Well-established methodologies such as conjoint analysis or discrete choice experiments (DCE) could be used for this purpose (see below).

²⁴ The variables included in two other studies provide a very marginal relationship with costs [108,117].

5.2.9. Analysis of fairness and public engagement

Procedural and distributional justice (fairness) and public engagement actions can affect social acceptance either directly, or indirectly (e.g. through trust, and perceived risks and benefits), but their role in this context has not been adequately studied [101]. Perceived procedural fairness in decision-making and trust in project developers generally increase project acceptance by local communities. “Voice”, which refers to the opportunity provided for local residents to express their opinions to a decision maker, is an important issue in this context. [104] argues that “no systematic analysis on the effectiveness of different types of voice opportunities (genuine voice vs. pseudo voice vs. no voice) offered to local communities in the context of these technologies has been conducted” [104, p.2] and provide a pioneering study on this topic, which should be followed by more research in the future.

5.2.10. The role of public policies

The role of public policies in increasing CCUS acceptance has been under-researched. Although virtually all the reviewed papers end up with recommendations for policies based on the findings on the most relevant drivers and barriers to acceptance, the inclusion of policies in the surveys themselves has been limited. Their influence may be mostly indirect, i.e., public policies that are developed specifically for CCUS may reduce the risk of CCUS projects, particularly those located close to people [119], which would increase acceptance. Assessments of those policies through mediation analysis should be undertaken, but the impact of more direct policies could also be evaluated, such as information provision. Further research should also investigate whether and under which circumstances providing monetary compensation to the local population enhances acceptance as well as the level of support which would be required to significantly reduce the level of opposition. It could also identify if there are more effective and cost-effective ways to increase local acceptance.

5.3. Methods in the analysis of CCUS acceptance

5.3.1. Cross-country analysis

The context in which the studies are carried out is an important element. Country differences, cultural differences and even local features can influence CCUS acceptance. Considering the local contexts is fundamental for recognising community and individual values, the places' attributes, the community's dynamics, and how the technology will likely interact with them, including its impacts, risks, and benefits [22]. There are a few cross-country analyses on CCUS acceptance [58, 59, 100, 101, 117, 120, 121] and more research on the role of those differences is needed. When research has been carried out in more than one country, it has usually focused on perceived risks and benefits or the examination of issues relevant to awareness or general views, rather than social acceptance [101]. Knowledge of country-specific differences in the acceptance of sustainable technologies is limited, as social science acceptance studies have often been carried out in a national context [103]. Cross-country analyses would help to identify the socioeconomic, institutional and cultural features of countries which make CCUS acceptance more likely. In particular, social acceptance in developing countries has received much less attention than in developed ones. This is unfortunate, given the potential role that CCUS can play to decarbonise the growing industrial sectors in those countries.

5.3.2. Trends overtime

The analysis of the trends of CCUS acceptance over time has received very scant research attention so far. The only analyses of CCUS acceptance over time are [122], which showed that the number of respondents who were “comfortable” with the presence of the Otway CCUS project in their region increased from 33% in 2006 to 48% in 2011, and [123] which found that, in China, public acceptance of CCS significantly increased from 21% in 2014 to 53% in 2021. Acceptance could be assumed to change over time, in line with the evolution of the

costs and increasing maturity of the technologies. It could also be related to changes in the socioeconomic, institutional and environmental context (e.g., reflecting an increasing concern on the urgency of climate change mitigation or the dependence on foreign energy sources). For a given geographical context, the drivers and barriers which influence CCUS acceptance may also evolve (e.g., climate change awareness may increase, or concerns about costs may change). An analysis of those trends (both regarding CCUS acceptance itself, as well as its influencing factors) would allow us to improve our knowledge on the impact of exogenous factors (energy crises) on CCUS acceptance.

Acceptance research has experienced some emerging trends. Recently, there has been a greater focus on CCUS as a way to decarbonise the industrial sectors rather than only as an alternative to decarbonise the power generation sector, where other (cheaper) options already exist. The utilisation stage has started to receive more attention, and research on its acceptance vs. other stages has been carried out (see 5.1.1). Finally, there have been more studies on developing countries. These trends will probably be consolidated in the future, as developing countries consider CCUS as a promising technology to decarbonise their hard-to-abate sectors and the move towards a Circular Economy makes carbon utilisation a relevant option. In contrast, a clear pattern could not be discerned regarding general CCUS acceptance vs a national or a local focus, although the general acceptance literature on CCUS (i.e., not only using survey studies) initially focused on NIMBY.

5.3.3. Beyond single stepwise multiple regressions: SEM and stated preferences methods

Some of the above proposals for future research require the use of methodologies which, although standard, have been little used in the analysis of CCUS acceptance in the past, which has mostly relied on linear regressions, with drivers and barriers included as explanatory variables. Those methodologies include structural equation modelling (SEM) and stated preference techniques, such as discrete choice experiments (DCE), or conjoint analysis.

Single stepwise multiple regression (generally with OLS estimation) has been the most common econometric method. They allow the identification of the relevance and direction of the relationship between individual factors and CCUS acceptance. Two papers use hierarchical regression analysis [99, 103], which allows investigating the incremental influence of impact factors by accounting for the impact of other factors. However, the mutual influences between each component are still disregarded when using these methods [123]. Although interaction terms may partly account for this, a proper methodology is mediation analysis, which can benefit from the use of a SEM approach. As argued by Ref. [92], SEM offers significant advantages with respect to traditional regression techniques in handling complex models, providing greater flexibility even in the absence of linearity and normality assumptions.

On the other hand, trade-offs could be analysed through stated preference techniques. Very few studies specifically use these techniques to estimate willingness to pay for CCUS ([67, 124, 125]). DCE and conjoint design surveys allow researchers to assess trade-offs between attributes and between policies, which are otherwise difficult to measure using traditional survey formats [126].

To sum up, this review suggests that some issues could receive more attention in the future, i.e., a greater focus on the transportation and utilisation stages, the acceptance of different sources of the CO₂ being captured or the origin of the source of CO₂ (foreign or domestic), the acceptance of DACCs and BECCs compared to CCUS in general and iCCS compared to the use of CCS for coal-fired power plants, the differential determinants of general vs. local acceptance, a greater focus on the comparative perception of CCUS as either a bridging technology or one leading to carbon lock-in, the need for a transdisciplinary theoretical framework which addresses some under-researched determinants of CCUS acceptance as well as their mediating effects and trade-offs, and a greater attention to specific drivers on CCUS acceptance, including the

role of public engagement, the influence of costs, types of information sources and public policies. A cross-country and dynamic analysis of those topics is recommendable. Some of them could more appropriately be addressed with new methods, including structural equation modelling and stated preference techniques. However, a very important challenge to perform those analysis will be their feasibility in terms of data availability.

6. Conclusions

Acceptance of CCUS has usually been considered as a main bottleneck for its deployment. Using a systematic literature review, we have identified the level of social acceptance of CCUS technologies worldwide in the existing literature, and the drivers and barriers of such acceptance. Our review has included articles in the literature which used surveys to the general public. The results show that, in general, social acceptance of CCUS is neutral to slightly positive. However, we also identify strong proximity (NIMBY) effects, as well as differences between storage and utilisation. Moreover, some factors emerge as relevant drivers and barriers to CCUS acceptance. Drivers include effectiveness in climate change mitigation, perception of benefits, knowledge and information on CCUS, as well as trust in information and relevant stakeholders. In addition to proximity, the main barriers to CCUS acceptance are related to perceived risks and mitigation deterrence. The article identifies some knowledge gaps on the topic and proposes several avenues for further research. It also derives some policy implications from the research. The identification of the most relevant barriers to CCUS acceptance has implications for the adoption of policies which mitigate those barriers and encourage its deployment.

As any paper, this one has limitations, which add further suggestions for research. First, it should be taken into account that a general assessment of the drivers and barriers to CCUS acceptance has been provided in this paper. This means that the national or local contexts have been disregarded, i.e., it has not been analysed if a particular driver or barrier plays a more important role in one specific country. This is a simplification, since the results on social acceptance are likely to depend on the context in which the CCUS projects are located. As argued by Ref. [22], “the public perception of CCS cannot be generalised due to heterogeneity in context, socio-economic characteristics, and respondents’ knowledge of and experiences with the industry” [22, p.4]. Still, broad picture and general patterns are provided. As mentioned above, future research should analyse the extent to which the context (and, particularly, different cultures, which are likely to affect the perception of benefits and risks) influence CCUS acceptance.

This paper uses an analytical framework based on four evaluation criteria which allows researchers to systematically assess and analyse qualitative results in reviews of drivers and barriers in a quantitative manner. A limitation of our review is related to the scoring method. The manual coding was based on the results of each paper (e.g., regression results) and, although relatively straightforward, there is certainly an element of subjectivity. The setting of thresholds for the different dimensions of the analysis is relative and also subjective. However, there is not a common standard in the literature which defines those thresholds. In addition, the outcome of the review does not change substantially if those were slightly different, as shown in the sensitivity analysis. Further research may refine both our proposed criteria and the procedure to define the thresholds.

Finally, our criterion to select articles (surveys to the general public) has led to a homogenous set of evidence which facilitates the aggregation and comparison of the results across studies. Obviously, any questionnaire leads to self-assessment and self-reported answers, which may be subject to response and social desirability biases [105]. These responses add subjectivity, biases and ‘illusory superiority’ in the responses [108]. In addition, this study did not consider previous research on CCUS acceptance which has used other methods (i.e., surveys to specialised CCUS stakeholders). Thus, future research should identify

whether the results of this review would differ significantly from reviews that use other target populations. Furthermore, greater weights can be given to specific articles in a systematic review according to their relevance for the subject which is being investigated [41]. For instance, recent studies could be weighted more than older ones, weights could take into account differences in methodological quality or temporal changes, or be based on sample representativeness indicators. Meta-analyses can also be conducted based on effect sizes. However, weighting was not applied in this SR given the inherent difficulties and subjectivity in selecting them.

The acceptance of CCUS is one of the key aspects that are discussed as a prerequisite for the successful implementation of CCUS projects, both in academics and business practice [127]. It is often argued that one of the most important barriers for CCUS is its low social acceptance [1,6,9]. The analysis of the drivers and barriers to public support for more CCUS projects is important because it helps policy-makers anticipate challenges in implementing CCUS initiatives by activating the drivers and mitigating the barriers. Thus, the analysis carried out in this paper is instrumental in ensuring that these technologies are socially accepted, contributing to the overall success and effectiveness of decarbonisation initiatives [85].

Declaration of competing interest

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2026.102198>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] IPCC, 6th Assessment Report WGIII, 2022.
- [2] Ariadne, Deutschland Auf Dem Weg Zur Klimaneutralität 2045, Kopernikus-Projekt Ariadne. Potsdam-Institut für Klimafolgen-forschung (PIK), Potsdam, 2021.
- [3] DENA, Leitstudie Aufbruch Klimaneutralität, 2021. Berlin.
- [4] Prognos, Klimaneutrales Deutschland 2045, Wie Deutschland seine Klimaziele schon vor 2050 erreichen kann. Zusammenfassung Im Auftrag Von Stiftung Klimaneutralität, Agora Energiewende Und Agora Verkehrswende, 2021.
- [5] UNFCCC, United Nations Climate Change Conference “COP30, 2025. Belem Brazil.
- [6] IRENA, World Energy Transitions Outlook 2022. 1.5° C Pathway, 2022, pp. 30–41.
- [7] IEA, Transforming Industry Through CCUS, 2019. Paris, France.
- [8] S. Paltsev, et al., Hard-to-Abate sectors: the role of industrial carbon capture and storage (CCS) in emission mitigation, Appl. Energy 300 (2021) 117322.
- [9] P. Tcvetkov, A. Cherepovitsyn, S. Fedoseev, Public perception of carbon capture and storage: a state-of-the-art overview, Heliyon 5 (12) (2019) e02845.

- [10] K. Witte, Social acceptance of carbon capture and storage (CCS) from industrial applications, *Sustainability* 13 (21) (2021).
- [11] US Congress, Carbon capture and storage in the United States, Congressional Budget Office: Washington DC (2023).
- [12] The White House, *The Long-term Strategy of the United States*, Pathways to net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050, United States Department of State and the United States Executive Office of the President: Washington DC (2021).
- [13] IEA, *An Energy Sector Roadmap to Carbon Neutrality in China*, 2021. Paris.
- [14] IEA, *Opportunities for Hydrogen Production with CCUS in China*, 2022. Paris.
- [15] Global CCS Institute, *CCUS Progress in China*. A Status Report, 2023. Beijing, China.
- [16] K. Jiang, et al., China's carbon capture, utilization and storage (CCUS) policy: a critical review, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 119 (2020).
- [17] European Commission, *COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL, THE COUNCIL, The European Economic And Social Committee, The Committee Of The Regions And The European Investment Bank A Clean Planet for all* A European Strategic long-term Vision for a Prosperous, Modern, Competitive and Climate Neutral Economy. Brussels, 28.11.2018 COM, 2018. 773 final. 2018.
- [18] IEA, *Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage: the Opportunity in Southeast Asia*, 2021. Paris.
- [19] IEA, *CCUS Projects Database*, IEA, Paris, 2024.
- [20] IEA, *Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage*, 2023.
- [21] European Commission, *Progress on Competitiveness of Clean Energy Technologies*, 15.11, COM, Brussels, 2022, p. 643, final. 2022.
- [22] R. Tardin-Coelho, B. Bharadwaj, P. Ashworth, Carbon capture utilisation and storage (CCUS) and public perceptions: a systematic literature review, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 145 (2025) 104393.
- [23] J.A. Nielsen, K. Stavrianakis, Z. Morrison, Community acceptance and social impacts of carbon capture, utilization and storage projects: a systematic meta-narrative literature review, *PLoS One* 17 (8) (2022) e0272409.
- [24] S. L'Orange Seigo, et al., Predictors of risk and benefit perception of carbon capture and storage (CCS) in regions with different stages of deployment, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 25 (2014) 23–32.
- [25] N.M.A. Huijts, E.J.E. Molin, L. Steg, Psychological factors influencing sustainable energy technology acceptance: a review-based comprehensive framework, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 16 (1) (2012) 525–531.
- [26] R. Wüstenhagen, M. Wolsink, M.J. Bürer, Social acceptance of renewable energy innovation: an introduction to the concept, *Energy Policy* 35 (5) (2007) 2683–2691.
- [27] P. Upham, C. Oltra, À. Boso, Towards a cross-paradigmatic framework of the social acceptance of energy systems, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 8 (2015) 100–112.
- [28] S. Batel, Research on the social acceptance of renewable energy technologies: past, present and future, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 68 (2020) 101544.
- [29] G. Ellis, N. Schneider, R. Wüstenhagen, Dynamics of Social Acceptance of Renewable Energy: an Introduction to the Concept, Elsevier, 2023 113706.
- [30] K.B. Jang, T.H. Woo, Implications of public acceptance assessments for site selections in the small modular reactors using system dynamics, *Energy Strategy Rev.* 55 (2024) 101526.
- [31] R. Wang, Public attitudes and sustainability perceptions towards nuclear power: evidence from Chinese social media data mining, *Energy Strategy Rev.* 62 (2025) 101928.
- [32] J. Osei, K. Brown, M. Nejati, Understanding the factors affecting social acceptance of solar energy technologies, *Energy Strategy Rev.* 61 (2025) 101861.
- [33] S. Benetti, D.D. Rodrigues, M. Grasso, Here comes the sun...? A systematic literature review of factors supporting or opposing solar energy initiatives, *Energy Strategy Rev.* 63 (2026) 102018.
- [34] J. Gaede, I.H. Rowlands, Visualizing social acceptance research: a bibliometric review of the social acceptance literature for energy technology and fuels, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 40 (2018) 142–158.
- [35] M. Wolsink, Social acceptance revisited: gaps, questionable trends, and an auspicious perspective, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 46 (2018) 287–295.
- [36] P. Del Río, M. Burguillos, C. Kiefer, Which are the main determinants of energy poverty? A systematic review of the literature, *Energy Effic.* 18 (2025) 58.
- [37] P. Del Río, J. Oviedo, Systematic literature review of empirical analysis on the social acceptability of Cal-based CCUS technologies. Deliverable D6.3 of the EU-funded Calby2030 Project, 2023. Madrid, Spain.
- [38] C. Peñasco, L.D. Anadón, E. Verdolini, Systematic review of the outcomes and trade-offs of ten types of decarbonization policy instruments, *Nat. Clim. Change* 11 (3) (2021) 257–265.
- [39] M.K. Linnenluecke, M. Marrone, A.K. Singh, Conducting systematic literature reviews and bibliometric analyses, *Australian journal of management* 45 (2) (2020) 175–194.
- [40] D. Denyer, D. Tranfield, Producing a systematic review, in: D.A. Buchanan, A. Bryman (Eds.), *The Sage Handbook of Organizational Research Methods*, Sage Publications Ltd., 2009, pp. 671–689.
- [41] B.K. Sovacool, J. Axsen, S. Sorrell, Promoting novelty, rigor, and style in energy social science: towards codes of practice for appropriate methods and research design, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 45 (2018) 12–42.
- [42] N.R. Haddaway, A.S. Pullin, The policy role of systematic reviews: past, present and future, *Springer Science Reviews* 2 (1–2) (2014) 179–183.
- [43] M. Grubb, et al., Induced innovation in energy technologies and systems: a review of evidence and potential implications for CO2 mitigation, *Environ. Res. Lett.* 16 (4) (2021).
- [44] P. del Río, C.P. Kiefer, Which policy instruments promote innovation in renewable electricity technologies? A critical review of the literature with a focus on auctions, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 89 (2022).
- [45] Y. Fournis, M.-J. Fortin, From social 'acceptance' to social 'acceptability' of wind energy projects: towards a territorial perspective, *J. Environ. Plann. Manag.* 60 (1) (2017) 1–21.
- [46] S. L'Orange-Seigo, S. Dohle, M. Siegrist, Public perception of carbon capture and storage (CCS): a review, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 38 (2014) 848–863.
- [47] B. Alexandre, et al., Acceptance and acceptability criteria: a literature review, *Cognit. Technol. Work* 20 (2018) 165–177.
- [48] R. Cowell, G. Bristow, M. Munday, Acceptance, acceptability and environmental justice: the role of community benefits in wind energy development, *J. Environ. Plann. Manag.* 54 (4) (2011) 539–557.
- [49] C.R. Jones, et al., The social acceptance of carbon dioxide utilisation: a review and research agenda, *Front. Energy Res.* (5) (2017).
- [50] J. Offermann-van Heek, et al., Trust and distrust in carbon capture and utilization industry as relevant factors for the acceptance of carbon-based products, *Front. Energy Res.* 6 (2018).
- [51] L. Engelmann, K. Arning, M. Ziefle, One step closer: laypeople's perception of production steps for manufacturing CO2-based jet fuel, *Energy Sustain. Soc.* 14 (1) (2024) 9.
- [52] E. Dütschke, et al., Differences in the public perception of CCS in Germany depending on CO2 source, transport option and storage location, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 53 (2016) 149–159.
- [53] A. Pullin, et al., Guidelines for Authors Environmental Evidence, 2018.
- [54] J. Zhu, W. Liu, A tale of two databases: the use of web of science and scopus in academic papers, *Scientometrics* 123 (1) (2020) 321–335.
- [55] A. Linzenich, K. Arning, M. Ziefle, Acceptance of energy technologies in context: comparing laypeople's risk perceptions across eight infrastructure technologies in Germany, *Energy Policy* 152 (2021) 112071.
- [56] W.-K. Moon, L.A. Kahlor, H.C. Olson, Understanding public support for carbon capture and storage policy: the roles of social capital, stakeholder perceptions, and perceived risk/benefit of technology, *Energy Policy* 139 (2020) 111312.
- [57] C.J. Midden, N.M. Huijts, The role of trust in the affective evaluation of novel risks: the case of CO2 storage, *Risk Anal. Int. J.* 29 (5) (2009) 743–751.
- [58] K. Pietzner, et al., Public awareness and perceptions of carbon dioxide capture and storage (CCS): insights from surveys administered to representative samples in six European countries, *Energy Proc.* 4 (2011) 6300–6306.
- [59] L. Whitmarsh, D. Xenias, C.R. Jones, Framing effects on public support for carbon capture and storage, *Palgrave Communications* 5 (1) (2019).
- [60] D. Schumann, E. Duetschke, K. Pietzner, Public perception of CO2 offshore storage in Germany: regional differences and determinants, *Energy Proc.* 63 (2014) 7096–7112.
- [61] Q. Li, et al., A Survey of public perception of CCUS in China, *Energy Proc.* 63 (2014) 7019–7023.
- [62] P. Ashworth, et al., Comparing how the public perceive CCS across Australia and China, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 86 (2019) 125–133.
- [63] M. de Best-Waldhober, et al., Informed public opinion in the Netherlands: evaluation of CO2 capture and storage technologies in comparison with other CO2 mitigation options, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 10 (2012) 169–180.
- [64] Z.-A. Chen, et al., A large national survey of public perceptions of CCS technology in China, *Appl. Energy* 158 (2015) 366–377.
- [65] M. Ferguson, P. Ashworth, Message framing, environmental behaviour and support for carbon capture and storage in Australia, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 73 (2021) 101931.
- [66] S. Shackley, C. McLachlan, C. Gough, The public perception of carbon dioxide capture and storage in the UK: results from Focus Groups and a Survey, *Clim. Policy* 22 (2005) 377–398.
- [67] J.D. Sharp, M.K. Jaccard, D.W. Keith, Anticipating public attitudes toward underground CO2 storage, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 3 (5) (2009) 641–651.
- [68] R.M. Krause, et al., "Not in (or under) my backyard": geographic proximity and public acceptance of carbon capture and storage facilities, *Risk Anal.* 34 (3) (2014) 529–540.
- [69] A.D. Boyd, J.D. Hmielowski, P. David, Public perceptions of carbon capture and storage in Canada: results of a national survey, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 67 (2017) 1–9.
- [70] Y. Guo, et al., The influence of narrative versus statistical evidence on public perception towards CCS in China: survey results from local residents in Shandong and Henan provinces, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 84 (2019) 54–61.
- [71] K. Arning, et al., Same or different? Insights on public perception and acceptance of carbon capture and storage or utilization in Germany, *Energy Policy* 125 (2019) 235–249.
- [72] L. Wallquist, et al., Public acceptance of CCS system elements: a conjoint measurement, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 6 (2012) 77–83.
- [73] A. Saito, K. Itoaka, M. Akai, Those who care about CCS—Results from a Japanese survey on public understanding of CCS, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 84 (2019) 121–130.
- [74] N.M.A. Huijts, C.J.H. Midden, A.L. Meijnders, Social acceptance of carbon dioxide storage, *Energy Policy* 35 (5) (2007) 2780–2789.
- [75] S. Perdan, C.R. Jones, A. Azapagic, Public awareness and acceptance of carbon capture and utilisation in the UK, *Sustain. Prod. Consum.* 10 (2017) 74–84.
- [76] D.C. Warren, et al., Predictors of attitudes toward carbon capture and storage using data on world views and CCS-specific attitudes, *Sci. Publ. Pol.* 41 (6) (2014) 821–834.

- [77] P. Devine-Wright, Rethinking NIMBYism: the role of place attachment and place identity in explaining place-protective action, *J. Community Appl. Soc. Psychol.* 19 (6) (2009) 426–441.
- [78] K. Glenk, et al., Spatial dimensions of stated preference valuation in environmental and resource economics: methods, trends and challenges, *Environ. Resour. Econ.* 75 (2) (2020) 215–242.
- [79] von Rothkirch and Ejderyan, *Anticipating the Social Fit of CCS Projects by Looking at Place Factors*, 2021.
- [80] J. Ladenburg, M. Zuch, J. Kim, Can acceptance of location-specific carbon capture and storage be tipped? The causal effects of information and question framing, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 150 (2026) 104566.
- [81] T.L. Cherry, et al., The development and deployment of low-carbon energy technologies: the role of economic interests and cultural worldviews on public support, *Energy Policy* 68 (2014) 562–566.
- [82] S. Pianta, A. Rinscheid, E.U. Weber, Carbon capture and storage in the United States: perceptions, preferences, and lessons for policy, *Energy Policy* 151 (2021) 112149.
- [83] P. Shah, J.Z. Yang, L. Kahlor, Psychological distance, risk perception, and affect: Texas residents' support for carbon capture and storage, *J. Risk Res.* (2022) 1–15.
- [84] M. de Best-Walldrober, D. Daamen, A. Faaij, Informed and uninformed public opinions on CO₂ capture and storage technologies in the Netherlands, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 3 (3) (2009) 322–332.
- [85] M.G. Fikru, N. Nguyen, Factors shaping public support for more carbon capture and storage projects in the United States, *Environ. Manag.* 74 (3) (2024) 425–438.
- [86] S. Brunsting, et al., CCS acceptability: social site characterization and advancing awareness at prospective storage sites in Poland and Scotland, *Oil & Gas Science and Technology—Revue d'IFP Energies nouvelles* 70 (4) (2015) 767–784.
- [87] K. Broecks, et al., How do people perceive carbon capture and storage for industrial processes? Examining factors underlying public opinion in the Netherlands and the United Kingdom, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 81 (2021) 102236.
- [88] C. Merk, et al., Don't send us your waste gases: public attitudes toward international carbon dioxide transportation and storage in Europe, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 87 (2022) 102450.
- [89] M. Zuch, J. Ladenburg, Navigating the information pathway to carbon capture and storage acceptance: patterns and insights from a literature review, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 105 (2023) 103283.
- [90] I. Dallo, et al., Social perspectives of carbon capture, transportation, utilization, and storage in Switzerland, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 114 (2024) 103588.
- [91] I. Haverkämper, W. Wilkowska, M. Ziefle, What makes people accept carbon capture and utilization products? Exploring requirements of use in the German population, *Front. Energy Res.* 11 (2023) 1248555.
- [92] Y. Zhou, et al., Decoding the mechanisms influencing public acceptance of carbon dioxide capture and storage technology in China, *Energy* 313 (2024) 133888.
- [93] E. Düttschke, Public perception of CCUS, in: CCUS Forum WG on Public Perception of CCUS - Working Group Paper, 2023.
- [94] J. Ladenburg, et al., Taking the carbon capture and storage, wind power, PV or other renewable technology path to fight climate change? Exploring the acceptance of climate change mitigation technologies—A Danish national representative study, *Renew. Energy* 220 (2024) 119582.
- [95] L. Yang, X. Zhang, K.J. McAlinden, The effect of trust on people's acceptance of CCS (carbon capture and storage) technologies: evidence from a survey in the People's Republic of China, *Energy* 96 (2016) 69–79.
- [96] B.W. Terwel, F. Harinck, N. Ellemers, D.D. Daamen, Going beyond the properties of CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) technology: how trust in stakeholders affects public acceptance of CCS, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 5 (2) (2011) 181–188.
- [97] X. Wang, K. Lo, Just transition: a conceptual review, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 82 (2021) 102291.
- [98] K. Stavrianakis, J. Nielsen, Z. Morrison, Public perception and acceptance of CCUS: preliminary findings of a qualitative case study in Greece, *Open Research Europe* 3 (2024) 205.
- [99] F. Große-Kreul, et al., Understanding public acceptance amidst controversy and ignorance: the case of industrial Carbon Capture and Storage in Germany, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 118 (2024) 103838.
- [100] A.-M. Dowd, et al., Investigating the link between knowledge and perception of CO₂ and CCS: an international study, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 28 (2014) 79–87.
- [101] S. Karytsas, et al., A transnational study on the determinants of social acceptance of carbon capture, transport, and storage (CCS), in: IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, IOP Publishing, 2023.
- [102] B.W. Terwel, E. ter Mors, D.D. Daamen, It's not only about safety: beliefs and attitudes of 811 local residents regarding a CCS project in Barendrecht, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 9 (2012) 41–51.
- [103] K. Arning, L. Engelmann, M. Ziefle, Ready to fly? Comparing acceptance and behavioral usage intentions of CO₂-based aviation fuels in four European countries, *Front. Energy Res.* 11 (2023) 1156709.
- [104] E. ter Mors, E. van Leeuwen, It matters to be heard: increasing the citizen acceptance of low-carbon technologies in the Netherlands and United Kingdom, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 100 (2023) 103103.
- [105] C. Sitinjak, S. Ebenzezer, J. Ober, Exploring public attitudes and acceptance of CCUS technologies in JABODETABEK: a cross-sectional study, *Energies* 16 (10) (2023) 4026.
- [106] S. Anders, U. Liebe, J. Meyerhoff, Cross-border CO₂ transport decreases public acceptance of carbon capture and storage, *Nat. Clim. Change* (2024) 1–4.
- [107] E. Cox, E. Spence, N. Pidgeon, Public perceptions of carbon dioxide removal in the United States and the United Kingdom, *Nat. Clim. Change* 10 (8) (2020) 744–749.
- [108] T. Pieri, A. Nikitas, A. Angelis-Dimakis, Public acceptance and willingness to pay for carbon capture and utilisation products, *Clean Technologies* 5 (1) (2023) 436–450.
- [109] K.T. Raimi, et al., Exploring public perceptions of carbon capture and utilization in the US, *Sustain. Prod. Consum.* 50 (2024) 314–326.
- [110] A. Linzenich, et al., Uncovering attitudes towards carbon capture storage and utilization technologies in Germany: insights into affective-cognitive evaluations of benefits and risks, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 48 (2019) 205–218.
- [111] K. Itaoka, et al., Influential information and factors for social acceptance of CCS: the 2nd round survey of public opinion in Japan, *Energy Proc.* 1 (1) (2009) 4803–4810.
- [112] K. Itaoka, A. Saito, M. Akai, Public acceptance of CO₂ capture and storage technology: a survey of public opinion to explore influential factors, in: *Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies* 7, Elsevier, 2005, pp. 1011–1019.
- [113] K. Itaoka, A. Saito, M. Akai, A study on roles of public survey and focus groups to assess public opinions for CCS implementation, *Energy Proc.* 4 (2011) 6330–6337.
- [114] K.S. Wolske, et al., Public support for carbon dioxide removal strategies: the role of tampering with nature perceptions, *Clim. Change* 152 (2019) 345–361.
- [115] T. Satterfield, S. Nawaz, G.P. St-Laurent, Exploring public acceptability of direct air carbon capture with storage: climate urgency, moral hazards and perceptions of the 'whole versus the parts', *Clim. Change* 176 (2) (2023) 14.
- [116] IRENA, *World Energy Transitions Outlook 2023. 1.5° C Pathway*, 2023.
- [117] K. Amikawa, S. Hirabayashi, T. Sato, Public acceptance of subsea underground carbon storage, *Energy Proc.* 4 (2011) 6345–6352.
- [118] P. Shah, et al., Framing climate change mitigation technology: the impact of risk versus benefit messaging on support for carbon capture and storage, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 119 (2022) 103737.
- [119] Q. Li, et al., Public awareness of the environmental impact and management of carbon dioxide capture, utilization and storage technology: the views of educated people in China, *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy* 19 (8) (2017) 2041–2056.
- [120] V. Kashintseva, et al., Consumer attitudes towards industrial CO₂ capture and storage products and technologies, *Energies* 11 (10) (2018) 2787.
- [121] F. Karimi, A. Toikka, General public reactions to carbon capture and storage: does culture matter? *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 70 (2018) 193–201.
- [122] T. Steeper, CO₂CRC Otway Project social research: assessing CCS community consultation, *Energy Proc.* 37 (2013) 7454–7461.
- [123] J. Xie, Y. Xian, G. Jia, An investigation into the public acceptance in China of carbon capture and storage (CCS) technology, *Mitig. Adapt. Strategies Glob. Change* 28 (5) (2023) 27.
- [124] K.P. Broecks, et al., Persuasiveness, importance and novelty of arguments about Carbon Capture and Storage, *Environ. Sci. Pol.* 59 (2016) 58–66.
- [125] J. Kraeusel, D. Möst, Carbon Capture and Storage on its way to large-scale deployment: social acceptance and willingness to pay in Germany, *Energy Policy* 49 (2012) 642–651.
- [126] C. Scott-Buechler, et al., Communities conditionally support deployment of direct air capture for carbon dioxide removal in the United States, *Commun. Earth Environ.* 5 (1) (2024) 175.
- [127] P. Stigson, J.J.K. Haug, in: N. CO₂ (Ed.), *Public Perceptions of CCS: State of the Art and the NORDICC Context*, 2015.

Further reading

- [128] C. Braun, Not in my backyard: CCS sites and public perception of CCS, *Risk Anal.* 37 (12) (2017) 2264–2275.
- [129] N. Koukoulas, et al., Current CO₂ capture and storage trends in Europe in a view of social knowledge and acceptance. A short review, *Energies* 15 (15) (2022) 5716.
- [130] P.R. Lima, et al., Environmental awareness and public perception on carbon capture and storage (CCS) in Brazil, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 111 (2021) 103467.
- [131] Y. Sun, et al., Comparing the explicit and implicit attitudes of energy stakeholders and the public towards carbon capture and storage, *J. Clean. Prod.* 254 (2020) 120051.
- [132] C. Braun, et al., Public perception of climate engineering and carbon capture and storage in Germany: survey evidence, *Clim. Policy* 18 (4) (2018) 471–484.
- [133] H. Duan, The public perspective of carbon capture and storage for CO₂ emission reductions in China, *Energy Policy* 38 (9) (2010) 5281–5289.
- [134] M. Ha-Duong, A. Nadaï, A.S. Campos, A survey on the public perception of CCS in France, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 3 (5) (2009) 633–640.
- [135] F. Karimi, A. Toikka, J.I. Hukkinen, Comparative socio-cultural analysis of risk perception of Carbon Capture and Storage in the European Union, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 21 (2016) 114–122.
- [136] M. Kaiser, et al., Development of CCS projects in Poland. How to communicate with the local public? *Energy Proc.* 51 (2014) 267–273.
- [137] S. L'Orange-Seigo, et al., Communication of CCS monitoring activities may not have a reassuring effect on the public, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 5 (6) (2011) 1674–1679.
- [138] C. Oltra, R. Sala, À. Boso, The influence of information on individuals' reactions to CCS technologies: results from experimental online survey research, *Greenhouse Gases: Sci. Technol.* 2 (3) (2012) 209–215.
- [139] B.W. Terwel, D.D. Daamen, Initial public reactions to carbon capture and storage (CCS): differentiating general and local views, *Clim. Policy* 12 (3) (2012) 288–300.

- [140] M. Wang, et al., Promoting support for carbon capture and storage with social norms: evidence from a randomized controlled trial in China, *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 74 (2021) 101979.
- [141] J.P. Moutenet, K. Bédard, M. Malo, Public awareness and opinion on CCS in the province of Québec, Canada, *Greenhouse Gases: Sci. Technol.* 2 (2) (2012) 126–135.
- [142] C.R. Palmgren, et al., Initial public perceptions of deep geological and oceanic disposal of carbon dioxide, *Environ. Sci. Pol.* 10 (2004) 6441–6450.
- [143] K. Tokushige, K. Akimoto, T. Tomoda, Public perceptions on the acceptance of geological storage of carbon dioxide and information influencing the acceptance, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 1 (1) (2007) 101–112.
- [144] E. Miller, L. Bell, E. Buys, Public understanding of carbon sequestration in Australia: socio-demographic predictors of knowledge, engagement and trust, *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Society* 5 (1) (2007) 15–33.
- [145] L. Toma, et al., A behavioural economics analysis of the impact of information and knowledge on CO2 capture and storage acceptance in the European Union, *Procedia Econ. Finance* 14 (2014) 605–614.
- [146] L. Wallquist, V.H. Visschers, M. Siegrist, Impact of knowledge and misconceptions on benefit and risk perception of CCS, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* (2010).
- [147] J. Offermann-van Heek, et al., Assessing public acceptance of the life cycle of CO2-based fuels: does information make the difference? *Energy Policy* 143 (2020) 111586.